

**COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF COLOR STABILITY AND
SURFACE ROUGHNESS OF NEW COMPOSITES FOLLOWING
IMMERSION IN DIFFERENT BEVERAGES**

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ABSTRACT

Aim:

To analyze the effect of three beverages (Red Wine, Coca-Cola, and Lemon Soda) on color stability and surface roughness of two different types of resin composites at various time intervals *in vitro*.

Materials and Methods:

A dual cure bulk fill composite and a self adhesive composite were used. Each material was randomly divided into four equal subgroups of 10 samples each according to the beverages used (Red wine , Coca-Cola, lemon soda, and Distilled water). The samples were immersed in each beverage for 10 minutes each day for 56 days. Color change and surface roughness measurements were noted at the baseline — 3,6,9 & 12 Weeks.

Results:

Self Adhesive composites were more stable in different beverages over time.

Conclusion:

The effect of interaction of different resin composites, various beverages, and time depended on a multitude of factors.

Keywords: Beverages, color change, resin composite, surface roughness, time

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INTRODUCTION

Esthetic failure is one of the most common reasons for the replacement of restorations. Color changes in resin composites occur from intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Intrinsic factors involve chemical changes in the material. Extrinsic factors, such as, adsorption or absorption of stains, pose a major problem for esthetic restorations. Surface roughness is one reason for exterior discoloration.[1]

Consumption of certain beverages may affect the esthetic and physical properties of the resin composite, thereby, undermining the quality of restorations.[2] The chemicals in beverages can lead to wear and surface degradation of composite restorations, resulting in unesthetic external pigmentation, such as, stains. Due to its low pH, ethanol can produce erosion and alter some properties of composites, as well.[3] Alcohol is also thought to act as a plasticizer of the polymer matrix.[4] It is not known if the alcohol in typical alcoholic beverages has a negative effect on the wear resistance of resin composites.

Different types of composites may behave differently. Currently nanocomposites are being increasingly used for posterior teeth. Of late, bulk fill and self adhesive composites have been introduced. The

effect of different beverages on these two types of materials is relatively unknown.

This knowledge is important to the practitioner for the selection of restorative material for the management of patients, where an exogenous erosive habit is under treatment.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Two visible light-cured resin composites were used in this study.

Group 1: Dual Cure Bulk Fill.(Coltene ,Waldent) M2 shade

Group 2: Self Adhesive Composite (Dentsply St. Paul, MN, USA)}. A2 shade

Forty disk-shaped samples (8 mm×2 mm) were prepared for each material using a Teflon mould.[5] The samples were cured as per the manufacturer's instructions.

Each disk was polished using the Super-Snap polishing system according to the manufacturer's instructions (Shofu Inc, Kyoto, Japan). The same operator polished all the samples in random sequence.

All the samples were stored at 37°C in distilled water for 24 hours for rehydration and completion of polymerization.[6]

After 24 hours of storage, each material was randomly divided into four subgroups of 10 samples each, according to the beverages used.

1. Group 1A and 2A: Distilled Water (Control)
2. Group 1B and 2B: Coca-Cola (Coca-Cola Company, India). pH=1.57
3. Group 1C and 2C: Lemon Soda (Pepsi Foods Pvt. Ltd., India). pH=2.32
4. Group 1D and 2D: Red Wine (John Distilleries Ltd., Bangalore). 42.8% v/v. pH=3.76

The samples were blotted dry using tissue paper and the baseline readings were obtained for Surface Roughness (Ra) and Color Change (ΔE) for each group.

Surface roughness was measured using a Profilometer, Surtronic 3+ (Taylor Hobson, Precision). The diamond stylus tip of 2 μm radius was placed at the extremity of the disk-shaped sample and it traversed the surface of the disk to trace a 4.8 mm course, providing the first measurement of Ra in micrometers. Two additional measurements were taken by rotating the disk to 90° and the mean Ra was obtained from the three values.[7]

Color change was measured using a Spectrophotometer, Spectrolino (Gretag-Macbeth AG, Germany). The color was assessed using the CIEL*a*b* measuring system. The color measurements were performed at the center of the resin composite disks and repeated thrice. The ΔE values were obtained for each sample and the mean of the values was calculated.[8]

After baseline readings the samples were immersed in the respective beverages. The immersion regimen followed was as follows: The samples in each group were immersed in the respective beverage for 10 minutes every day. For the remaining part of the day, the samples were kept immersed in distilled water. This regimen was followed for 12 weeks. Surface roughness and color measurements were checked on the 3rd, 6th, 9th & 12th week.

For statistical analysis, SPSS for windows V. 11.5 was used. Repeated Measures of analysis of variance (RANOVA) and the Bonferroni test were used to find the difference in color change and surface roughness in the two resin composites when immersed in distilled water, Coca-Cola, Lemon Soda, and Red Wine. The Pearson Correlation test was performed to test if any correlation existed between color change and surface roughness.

RESULTS:

There were three variables in this study: Two resin composites, four immersion solutions, and five time intervals. The interaction between these three variables produced statistically significant results in color change ($P < 0.001$; $F = 53.581$) and surface roughness ($P < 0.001$; $F = 12.879$).

When discoloration of the two resin composites was considered, the overall maximum discoloration took place in the Bulk fill Composite when compared with the Self Adhesive Composite, and the results were statistically significant.

When discoloration in different beverages was considered, maximum discoloration took place in Coca-Cola > Red Wine > Lemon Soda and minimum in Distilled water. (Table1)

When change in surface roughness of the two resin composites was considered, the overall maximum surface roughness change took place in the bulk fill composite as compared to the self adhesive composite and the results were statistically significant.

When the surface roughness change in different beverages was considered, the maximum change in surface roughness took place in Coca-Cola > Red Wine > Lemon Soda and minimum in Distilled water. (Table 2)

The Pearson Correlation test showed a correlation of 0.936 for Ra values and 1 for Delta E values.

Table 1. Color Stability

Staining Solution	Composite	Time Interval				
		Baseline	3 weeks	6 weeks	9 weeks	12 weeks
Red wine	Self Adhesive	2.32 (1.24-2.82)	2.30 (1.25-2.75)	2.29 (1.27-3.46)	2.35 (1.16-3.83)	2.76 (1.96-4.69)
	Dual Cure Bulk fill	0.66 (0.30-1.75)	0.75 (0.17-1.74)	0.72 (0.32-1.26)	0.95 (0.31-1.49)	0.78 (0.38-1.21)
Lemon soda	Self Adhesive	12.00 (10.74-13.72)*	14.43 (12.93-15.62)*	15.38 (13.98-16.86)*	20.36 (18.51-21.79)*	25.63 (24.25-27.41)*
	Dual Cure Bulk fill	18.96 (17.45-20.28)*	21.66 (20.10-21.13)*	23.22 (21.25-24.60)*	27.69 (25.57-29.43)*	30.04 (28.09-30.97)*
Coca Cola	Self Adhesive	1.73 (0.93-2.88)	2.10 (0.51-2.92)	2.07 (0.65-3.06)	2.06 (0.65-3.34)	2.56 (0.63-3.56)
	Dual Cure Bulk fill	2.13 (1.53-3.29)	2.19 (1.38-3.39)	2.21 (1.66-2.94)	2.82 (2.13-3.46)	2.83 (2.08-4.03)

Distilled water	Self Adhesive	2.37 (1.93–3.20)	2.75 (2.19–3.47)	3.42 (2.49–4.14)*	5.03 (4.49–6.57)*	8.32 (7.62–9.92)*
	Dual Cure Bulk fill	8.70 (7.42–9.87)*	10.51 (9.57–11.40)*	11.58 (10.66–12.83)*	18.09 (17.16–19.81)*	20.93 (19.83–22.67)*
*Indicates clinically unacceptable values ($\Delta E > 3.3$).						

Table 2. Means and standard deviations for surface roughness measurements for the specimens immersed in different beverages

Storage solution	Composites	After 1 week	After 3 weeks	After 6 weeks	After 9 weeks	After 12 week
Red wine	Dual Cure	0.077 (0.001)	0.074 (0.006)	0.070 (0.007)	0.070 (0.010)	0.076 (0.008)
	Self Adhesive	0.066 (0.005)	0.068 (0.008)	0.0697 (0.006)	0.072 (0.004)	0.07 (0.007)
	Sonic Fill	0.070 (0.005)	0.072 (0.008)	0.077 (0.006)	0.078 (0.004)	0.080(0.007)
Lemon Soda	Dual Cure	0.071 (0.003)	0.076 (0.005)	0.078 (0.008)	0.074 (0.005)	0.070 (0.003)
	Self Adhesive	0.0793 (0.012)	0.0827 (0.004)	0.0807 (0.007)	0.0807 (0.007)	0.078 (0.008)
	Sonic Fill	0.077 (0.001)	0.074 (0.006)	0.070 (0.007)	0.070 (0.010)	0.076 (0.008)
Distilled water	Dual Cure	0.072 (0.002)	0.072 (0.005)	0.072 (0.008)	0.074 (0.011)	0.066 (0.005)
	Self Adhesive	0.074 (0.014)	0.068 (0.008)	0.084 (0.005)	0.074 (0.005)	0.079 (0.01)
	Sonic Fill	0.065 (0.005)	0.069 (0.008)	0.071 (0.006)	0.077 (0.004)	0.080 (0.007)
Coca cola	Dual Cure	0.070 (0.005)	0.077 (0.005)	0.076 (0.005)	0.068 (0.004)	0.080 (0.000)
	Self Adhesive	0.0827 (0.004)	0.084 (0.005)	0.0778 (0.008)	0.0807 (0.001)	0.076 (0.009)
	Sonic Fill	0.073 (0.005)	0.075 (0.008)	0.078 (0.006)	0.082 (0.004)	0.084(0.007)

DISCUSSION:

The present study was conducted on two resin composites; one was a dual cure bulk fill composite and the other was a self adhesive composite. Long-term clinical performance and color stability of the nanofilled composites are yet to be known

and proven. Similarly, the silorane-based resin composite is a relatively recent product and has not been researched on its degradation under acidic conditions and color stability.

In the present study, surface roughness assessment was chosen because surface micromorphology would effect the staining susceptibility. The CIEL*a*b* system for measuring the chromaticity was chosen to record color differences, because it is well-suited for the determination of small color differences.[9]

Commonly consumed alcoholic (Whiskey) and nonalcoholic beverages (Coca-Cola and Nimbooz) were used as the discoloration media in the present study, to evaluate the discoloration of resin composites in an *in vitro* setting. Among the alcoholic beverages, previous studies have evaluated the effect of red wine on the discoloration of a resin composite. As the consumption of whiskey is presumably higher and more prevalent than red wine, it became even more reasonable to select it as one of the staining solutions.

During consumption, food or drink comes in brief contact with the tooth surfaces before it is washed away by saliva. However, in the previous studies, substrates usually contacted acidic foodstuff for a prolonged period of time. Thus, the immersion regimen selected was to immerse each sample in the respective beverage for ten minutes each day. For the remaining part of the day the samples were kept in distilled water to mimic the

neutralizing effect of saliva. The measurement of color change and surface roughness was made at different time intervals (baseline, the seventh, fourteenth, twenty-eighth, and fifty-sixth day) to see the relationship of time on surface degradation.

According to the results of this study, both materials became significantly stained and rougher after they were subjected to the immersion regimen. This can be ascribed to the capability of acid media to soften resin-based restorative materials.[10]

Overall, the maximum change in both color and surface roughness took place in methacrylate-based composite as compared to silorane-based composite and the results were statistically significant. This result could be explained on the basis of different chemical compositions of both the materials. Ceram-X is a nanohybrid composite containing methacrylate-modified polysiloxane and dimethacrylate resin, while Filtek P90 contains a silorane resin. Both had comparable filler loading: 76% (w/w) and 57% (v/v) for Ceram-X and 76% (w/w) and 55% (v/v) for Filtek P90. Thus, the degradation that took place could not be attributed to its higher/lower resin content. This was in accordance with the observations made in the previous studies, which stated that relatively small

differences in the filler-resin ratio could not explain variations in water sorption.[2,11]

Staining of resins by beverages is caused by the adsorption or absorption of colorants by the resins[12] and the resin's affinity for extrinsic stains is modulated by its water sorption rate.[1,13] Methacrylate-modified polysiloxane and dimethacrylate resins may have higher water sorption compared to the silorane resin. Siloranes may be extremely hydrophobic, perhaps making the oxirane groups inaccessible to attack by water or water-soluble species.[14] The increased synergism between filler particles and resin matrix may be responsible for the reduction in water sorption and solubility.[15] Also nanohybrid fillers seem to be less color-resistant than the micron-sized fillers due to the former's relatively high water sorption character.[16]

As the interface between the resin and filler particles is one of the weakest points of the composite material, with a high sensitivity to water sorption, it may be supposed that hydrolytic degradation of this interface can modify the way in which light is scattered by the particles.[11]

In this study the Pearson Correlation test showed that there was a correlation

between both the tested parameters. The smoother the surface, the more resistant the material was to staining.[1]

When different beverages were compared, Coca-Cola had the most degrading effect on both the parameters followed by Red Wine and Lemon Soda. No significant change was seen in distilled water. All the beverages used in the study were acidic with Coca-Cola being the most acidic (pH=1.57)>Lemon Soda (pH=2.32)>Red Wine (pH=3.76). Lower pH was seen to negatively affect the wear resistance of composite materials.[17] Lower pH increased the erosion in polymers.[18] Thus, the higher degradation that took place in Coca-Cola could be attributed to its lower pH. However, Lemon Soda showed a lower degradation than Whiskey. This result could be due to the alcohol content of Whiskey (42.8% v/v), as solvents such as ethanol penetrate the resin matrix.[19] Studies have shown sub-superficial degradation, expansion, and inferior physical properties when Bis-GMA-based composites were exposed to the ethanol solvent.[20]

More surface roughness change in Coca-Cola than Whiskey is supported by an earlier study, in which Coca-Cola caused a significant increase in surface roughness than sugar cane spirit (alcoholic graduation 39.00% v/v).[7]

When discoloration in Coca-Cola and alcoholic beverages is compared, the result of the present study is conflicting. However, the previous studies compared the staining ability of Coca-Cola with red wine, in which red wine caused more color change.[9,21,22] Cola gains its color through the addition of caramel color and red wine, mainly from grapes. Probably the caramel in Coca-Cola has more staining ability than the colorants present in Whiskey.

Time was found to be a critical factor for the color stability of tooth colored restorative materials. In the present study, results showed that as the immersion time increased, the color changes became more intense.[23]

Values of ΔE^* greater than or equal to 3.3 are visually perceptible and clinically unacceptable to 50% of the trained observers.[24]

In this study, in the bulk fill composite, ΔE^* in the Coca-Cola group crossed the 3.3 level around the fourteenth day, while in the red wine group it crossed after the twenty-eighth day. In lemon soda and the distilled water group ΔE^* was below 2 at all time intervals. Although in the self adhesive composite, the ΔE^* in the Coca-Cola group crossed the 3.3 level around the twenty-eighth day while in the red

wine group it crossed near the fifty-sixth day. In the lemon soda and distilled water group, the ΔE^* was below 2 at all time intervals.

It is difficult to extrapolate the results of this study to *in vivo* conditions. However, the results of this study can give an insight into how different resin composites may behave when exposed to different beverages, thus affecting the clinician's choice of material and the patient's control of dietary habits.

CONCLUSION

The results of this *in vitro* staining and surface roughness study showed that the effect of interaction of different resin composites, various beverages, and time, depended on a multitude of factors.

- The self adhesive composite exhibited better color stability and relatively lower surface roughness when compared to bulk fill composites in alcoholic and nonalcoholic beverages
- Coca-cola, among the three beverages, caused the highest discoloration and surface roughness change in both the tested resin composites
- Both the resin composites exhibited increased staining and surface roughness

change, over time, on selective exposure to alcoholic and nonalcoholic beverages

REFERENCES:

1. Lu H, Roeder LB, Lei L, Powers JM. Effect of surface roughness on stain resistance of Dental resin composites. *J Esthet Restor Dent.* 2005;17:102–9. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
2. Dietschi D, Campanile G, Holz J, Meyer JM. Comparison of the color stability of ten new-generation composites: An *in vitro* study. *Dent Mater.* 1994;10:353–62. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
3. Sarret DC, Coletti, Peluso AR. The effect of alcoholic beverages on composite wear. *Dent Mater.* 2000;16:62–7. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. Ferracane JL, Marker VA. Solvent degradation and reduced fracture toughness in aged composites. *J Dent Res.* 1994;92:257–61. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
5. Turkun LS, Turkun M. The effect of one-step polishing system on the surface roughness of three esthetic resin composite materials. *Oper Dent.* 2004;29:203–11. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
6. Topcu FT, Sahinkesen G, Yamanel K, Erdemir U, Oktay EA, Ersahan S. Influence of different drinks on the colour stability of dental resin composites. *Eur J Dent.* 2009;3:50–6. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
7. Badra VV, Faraoni JJ, Ramos RP, Palma-Dibb RG. Influence of different beverages on the microhardness and surface roughness of resin composites. *Oper Dent.* 2005;30:213–9. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
8. Ergucu Z, Turkun S, Aladag A. Color stability of nanocomposites polished with one-step systems. *Oper Dent.* 2008;33:413–20. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
9. Guler AU, Yilmaz F, Kulunk T, Guler E, Kurt S. Effects of different drinks on stainability of resin composite provisional restorative materials. *J Prosthet Dent.* 2005;94:118–24. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
10. Gao F, Matsuya S, Ohta M, Zhang J. Erosion process of light-cured and conventional glass ionomer cements in citrate buffer solution. *Dent Mater J.* 1997;16:170–9. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
11. Vichi A, Ferrari M, Davidson CL. Color and opacity variations in three different resin-based composite products after water aging. *Dent Mater.* 2004;20:530–4. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

12. Gupta G, Gupta T. Evaluation of the effect of various beverages and food material on the color stability of provisional materials - an *in vitro* study. *J Conserv Dent*. 2011;14:287-92. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
13. De Gee AJ, Ten Harkel-Hagenaar E, Davidson CL. Color dye for identification of incompletely cured composite resins. *J Prosthet Dent*. 1984;52:626-31. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
14. Eick JD, Smith RE, Pinzino CS, Kostoryz EL. Stability of silorane dental monomers in aqueous systems. *J Dent*. 2006;34:405-10. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
15. Palin WM, Fleming GJP, Burke FJ, Marquis PM, Randall RC. The influence of short and medium-term water immersion on the hydrolytic stability of novel low-shrink dental composites. *Dent Mater*. 2005;21:852-63. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
16. Ertas E, Guler AU, Yucel A, Koprulu H, Guler E. Color stability of resin composites after immersion in different drinks. *Dent Mater J*. 2006;25:371-6. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
17. Chadwick RG, McCabe JF, Walls AW, Storer R. The effect of storage media upon the surface microhardness and abrasion resistance of three composites. *Dent Mater*. 1990;6:123-8. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
18. Ortengren U, Andersson F, Elgh U, Terse Lius B, Karisson S. Influence of pH and storage time on the sorption and solubility behaviour of three composite resin materials. *J Dent*. 2001;29:35-41. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
19. Ahmed KI, Sajjan G. Color stability of ionomer and resin composite restoratives in various environmental solutions: An invitro reflection spectrophotometric study. *J Conserv Dent*. 2005;8:45-51. [Google Scholar]
20. Lee SY, Huang HM, Liin CY, Shilh YR. Leached components from dental composites in oral simulating fluids and the resultant composite strengths. *J Oral Rehab*. 1998;25:575-88. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
21. Patel SB, Gordan VV, Barrett AA, Shen C. The effect of surface finishing and storage solutions on the color stability of resin-based composites. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2004;135:587-94. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
22. Bagheri R, Burrow MF, Tyas M. Influence of food-simulating solutions and surface finish on susceptibility to staining of aesthetic restorative materials. *J Dent*. 2005;33:389-98. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

23. Abu-Bakr N, Han L, Okamoto A, Iwaku M. Color stability of compomer after immersion in various media. *J Esthet Restor Dent.* 2000;12:258-63. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
24. Ruyter IE, Nilner K, Moller B. Color stability of dental composite resin materials for crown and bridge veneers. *Dent Mater.* 1987;3:246-51. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

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